

THE IMPORTANCE OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE IN CLASSROOM SETTING

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Abstract. *In today’s emotionally demanding classrooms, a teacher’s success depends not only on knowledge but also on the power to understand and manage emotions - making emotional intelligence an essential tool in modern education. Studies have shown that higher EQ leads to lower levels of stress, higher rates of positive emotional states and happiness, and better health and well-being. Drawing on recent research and evidence-based practices, it examines how EI contributes to a supportive learning environment and strengthens a teacher’s ability to navigate daily challenges. This article explores the critical role emotional intelligence plays in enhancing teaching effectiveness, promoting positive student-teacher relationships, and reducing stress and burnout among educators.*

Keywords: *Emotional intelligence, emotional quotient, self-regulation, empathy, interpersonal relationships, active listening, enthusiasm in learning, proactive methods in teaching, strong social skills.*

Introduction

Beginning with clarifying what is Emotional Intelligence (EI), this refers to recognizing, managing and handling one’s emotions along with others’. Emotional intelligence, also considered as Emotional Quotient (EQ), provides navigating social situations effectively. Self-awareness, motivation, self-regulation, social skills and empathy are five key elements of EI. High emotional intelligent individuals have ability to identify what they are feeling, what those feelings mean and how they influence their attitude. People with top-level of EI are often valued not only in job markets, but interpersonal communication as well. Highlighting the role of EI in teaching can help teachers to enhance relationships with students. Successful leaders are often emotional intelligent, helping being self-aware and able to approach things objectively, thus leading to be valued by employers and creating opportunities in the workforce. In this regard, developing EI is significant for teachers to enhance their professional efficiency and personal well-being.

Main part: Emotion regulation in educational settings

Emotionally intelligent teachers are known to be highly effective, creative, empathetic, caring and supportive, they convey a lot of enthusiasm and confidence in their job. Such teachers can create safe, positive and physical learning environments in their classrooms (Galler, 2015). Teachers utilise their emotional skills such as empathy and motivation to develop interpersonal relationships with their students. In this way students will feel safe and free making way for effective teaching and learning to take place (Tok et al., 2013). Over time teachers will use their motivational skills to access the feelings of their students to create bonds and sustain them (Brackett & Katalak, 2006). In addition to the above mentioned, Jennings and Greenberg (2009) assert that emotionally intelligent teachers have sufficient self-awareness to recognise their weakness and strengths in controlling and managing their emotions.

Active listening as a pedagogical tool

One aspect of emotional intelligence can be seen as active listening. As Carl Rogers said “We think we listen, but very rarely do we listen with real understanding, true empathy. Yet listening, of this very special kind is one of the most potent forces for change that I know”. As educators active listening can help create a space where students can think more clearly about what they are saying and thinking. As a result, active listening can be a powerful tool to help establish care for all students and facilitate student agency, as well as support an inclusive teaching environment. (Rogers Lyon, Tausch, 2014).

Empathy and student-centered teaching

It is common for teachers rather focusing more on students’ negative behaviour than teaching, resulting in inadequate classroom environment. Amanda Morin (Educational and neurodiversity consultant) once said, “Empathy may not be about feeling sorry, but it is about feelings. You may need to take a minute to regroup before you talk to the student.”

Having a stressful moment, you should give yourself permission to admit your own emotions since it is natural to be upset or frustrated.

EI contributes positively in the classroom because teachers are more proactive, instead of always resorting to punitive and coercive measures. Teachers are able to support students by emotionally expressing themselves verbally to promote enthusiasm and satisfaction in learning. Emotionally intelligent teachers have moved from punitive measures to more authoritative and proactive methods of teaching. These methods assist in the formation of rules, encourage cooperation, develop supportive relationships, and promote academic engagement and student dedication towards school work. In such a classroom, a teacher knows how to help students tap into their social, emotional and academic success while being responsible for their actions. Teachers with EI create democratic learning environments that are empathetic to students’ needs and background, they help students find solutions to problems, they engage students in learning; physically, socially and emotionally, to avoid negative behavioral responses. (Refilwe Molatodi, 2018)

Social competence and professional collaboration

The American Psychological Association (APA) defines social skills as “a set of learned abilities that enable an individual to interact competently and appropriately in a given social context.” In simpler terms, social skills are what people use to successfully interact with others. It is important to note that social skills include both verbal and non-verbal communication, and strong social skills are demonstrated by a person’s ability to successfully live, work and understand others. (Adam Nance). In order to lead fulfilled classroom environment, emotional intelligence comes to help teachers, allowing them to work with others, resolve conflict, and build and sustain relationships. This makes teaching social skills such a vital function of our education systems, and equipping teachers with the tools they need to teach these skills is even more necessary.

Developing and enhancing emotional intelligence in teachers

Developing emotional intelligence is an ongoing process. The journey differs from person to person. Nonetheless, according to Andrews, the following actions may lead you to better self-awareness, empathy, and social skills. Audit your self-perception by asking managers, colleagues, friends, or family how they would rate your emotional intelligence. For example, ask them about how you respond to difficult situations, how adaptable or empathetic you are, and/or how well you handle conflict. It may not always be what you want to hear, but it will often be what you need to hear. (Andrew, 2019). In today’s dynamic and emotionally rich classrooms, teachers are expected

to do much more than deliver academic content. They must connect, inspire, and manage a wide range of emotions - their own and their students’.

Conclusion

Emotional intelligence is not just an added benefit - it is a necessity for today’s educators. Attending workshops, reading books or participating in professional learning communities focused on social-emotional skills can greatly enhance a teacher’s emotional competence. By becoming more self-aware, empathetic, and emotionally resilient, teachers not only improve their own well-being, but also create a more supportive and successful learning environment for their students.

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